

EU-HIP – DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

EU interoperability with HERA's IT platform

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WP 1 – Project Management and Coordination

DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

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INTRODUCTION AND GENERAL INFORMATION

This document is the first version of the Data Management Plan (DMP) for the EU-HIP project. The DMP is a key element of data management during a project covering the life cycle of the data from collection to availability and long-term storage.

The main purpose of EU-HIP DMP is first and foremost to be a living document providing relevant metadata and information about the data collected and used in the EU-HIP project. This document outlines the principles, policies, and procedures for managing data within the EU-HIP project. As a living document, the DMP will evolve during the EU-HIP project as data sources, metadata categories, procedures etc. are added, developed, changed, or discarded.

The first iteration of the DMP focuses on general aspects of data expected to be collected, and on EU-HIP partner efforts in consolidating and integrating selected databases and data sources at organization or country level, developing internal APIs for data sharing, as well as initial concepts for external APIs for interoperability with upcoming Intelligence Gathering, Threat Assessment, and Medical Counter-Measures information system of HERA (hereafter the IGTA/MCM system).

Building upon this work, as well as insight into the ongoing development of the IGTA/MCM system, later iteration of the DMP will be expanded to include more detailed descriptions of shared and sharable data including metadata.

EU-HIP will do its best to make data findable, accessible, interoperable and re-usable (FAIR-principle). Ethical considerations, GDPR, data security and Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) are considered along the process. Special focus is placed on interoperability and sustainability.

The EU-HIP DMP will align with the upcoming European Health Data Space Regulation. Within this document HERA is treated as a Union institution, office and/or agency and thus has the legal right to access electronic health data for an extended period of time with the goal of fulfilling the mandate.

FAIR PRINCIPLES

The EU-HIP project is committed to following the FAIR principles. The FAIR principles are a set of guidelines designed to enhance the accessibility, usability, and interoperability of digital resources, including research data. FAIR stands for:

1. **Findable:** Data and resources should be easy to find and locate by humans and machines. This involves providing clear and persistent identifiers, metadata, and comprehensive descriptions that enable effective search and discovery.
2. **Accessible:** Data and resources should be easily accessible, preferably through open access mechanisms, without unnecessary barriers or restrictions. This includes providing open and standardized protocols, authentication mechanisms, and appropriate access controls.
3. **Interoperable:** Data and resources should be able to be combined, integrated, and used in conjunction with other data and resources. Achieving interoperability involves using standard data formats, employing controlled vocabularies and ontologies, and ensuring compatibility with existing data infrastructure and tools.

4. Reusable: Data and resources should be well-documented, with clear and comprehensive metadata, providing sufficient information for users to understand and effectively reuse the data. Additionally, licensing and proper data citation practices should be employed to ensure proper attribution and recognition of data contributors.

By adhering to these principles, data are accessible and usable for a wide range of purposes, facilitating data-driven discoveries, collaboration, and innovation. For EU-HIP specifically, the focus is on interoperability, including supporting work towards standardization.

EXAMPLES OF WORK PACKAGE AND PARTNER ACTIONS RELATED TO DATA MANAGEMENT

The Work Packages (WPs) and partners of EU-HIP have started to work on gathering relevant data descriptions for the DMP. In this paragraph, selected examples of the performed and planned actions relating to data management and integration towards interoperability are presented. The examples selected cover activities across different technical maturity and organizational readiness levels and across countries participating in the EU-HIP project.

Sciensano is developing a new data collection system for Epilabo (a Belgian network of more than 50 sentinel clinical microbiology laboratories for 43 pathogens) via the Healthdata.be platform. This activity is performed with the aim of developing the robustness, harmonization, security and integrity of a digital system for data collection on laboratory test results at national level for surveillance of infectious diseases and communicating data. The system allows (near) real-time data transfer to partners such as the regional health authorities, the generation of automated feedback and reports to the collaborating laboratories and to health authorities. The laboratories will be able to set up a system-to-system data transfer in bulk via the new HD4DP 2.0 application, developed by Healthdata.be.

FIGURE 1 HIGH LEVEL OVERVIEW OF DATA FLOW THROUGH HEALTHDATA.BE

Sciensano is also supporting the development of the Pedisurv project: a digital surveillance system for 6 pediatric diseases also held at Healthdata.be, that aims to combine different data sources, depending on the disease, to monitor certain serious and/or rare infectious diseases in children under the age of 15.

Lastly, Sciensano is exploring the possibilities of data linkages between existing health data registries (e.g. Epilabo with mortality data, or with medication reimbursement data as proxy for health conditions). The objective is to enrich the data of laboratory test results with important outcomes such as mortality to assess the impact of infectious diseases or of interventions such as a vaccination campaign or a prevention program.

For Epilabo related activities, international standards will be used for coding the laboratory test results and their corresponding pathogens, sample type and test methods (LOINC and SNOMED-CT codes). This list of codes is being developed in collaboration with clinical microbiologists and epidemiologists, taking into account eHealth/ReTaM initiatives. In addition, the new data collection is based on the unique Belgian national registry number, which could enable linkage between different health databases for research and surveillance purposes. The nominative aspect of the new data collection enables its use as support in the context of mandatory notifiable diseases, which is one of the missions of regional and federal health authorities. These are thus working in close collaboration with Sciensano to improve the regional coverage of mandatory notifiable infectious diseases surveillance. Sciensano's legal team also works in collaboration with the Epilabo team to formalize the data transfer between partners and the collection of personal data considering GDPR. Laboratories are also consulted on the technical requirements for the new data collection and transfer.

Statens Serum Institut (SSI) has started to work on planning the development of a data catalog in accordance with the FAIR principles for easy overview of data, as well as planning APIs for accessing data. By developing and deploying IT infrastructure and preparing for more robust, connect/interoperable services, SSI is taking steps towards data interoperability. By the end of 2023, SSI will move from planning to developing the data catalog and expanding the staff for developing IT infrastructure and exploring the use of Natural Language Processing (NLP) AI. The short-term goal is to share metadata on bacteria between associated departments within SSI in the same way as for SARS-CoV-2/COVID-19 data. Data management aspects of related projects, in particular DURABLE, are considered in cross-project collaboration, as relevant for the objectives of EU-HIP.

The Italian Ministry of Health (MIN-SAL) has been working on the establishment of a coordinated communication mechanism among the various sectoral offices responsible for the collection, monitoring and management of health data. In this perspective, a series of internal meeting and knowledge-sharing roundtables have been carried out in the past months. The implementation of these preparatory activities has an essential basis on the FAIR principles, ensuring at the same time compliance with the national and European ethical-legal framework, in consideration of the high level of confidentiality of the data processed. Further steps on the reusability aspect are currently under evaluation, since there isn't a legally binding procedure at national level for the reuse of health data.

Based on the Italian *Pandemic Influenza Plan* (PanFlu 2021-2023), MIN-SAL intends to develop 2 systems: a rapid alert system based on the number of accesses to the emergency room for predetermined respiratory syndromes and an information system for monitoring health services to be activated quickly in the event of a health emergency. These systems would complement the existing monitoring systems in the field of health prevention (such as vaccines and outbreaks of infectious diseases, health checks on incoming goods). The different alert systems currently under development by MIN-SAL will be made interoperable through the actions developed within the EU-HIP project. MIN-SAL is committed in integrating into the Italian systems collecting health data from the Regions the standards adopted at European level (e.g., HL7 FHIR, CDA2) for interoperability of health data for both primary (e.g., NCPeH) and secondary use (e.g., TEHDAS and EHDS).

The Norwegian Institute of Public Health (NIPH) has focused on attaining an overview of major EU-projects, which have established a path for interoperability in the secondary use of health data. NIPH will follow these existing best practices in data interoperability and data management. Where possible NIPH will also use international standards and already established frameworks for data access, storage, retention, and sharing.

For NIPH as well as other EU-HIP partners, the EU-HIP Landscape Analysis will be important to clarify where the best opportunities for data sharing are located and to commence actions and start sharing data with HERA IGTA/MCM system. Norway has many national registries that are good candidates for sharing of data to the IGTA/MCM system.

The Shared Services of the Ministry of Health of Portugal (SPMS) is responsible for managing the MyHealth@EU services in Portugal, that provides a secure infrastructure for the cross-border exchange of electronic health service, such as Patient Summary and ePrescription / eDispensation. The contribution of these services into the IGTA/MCM system will depend on establishing guidelines and specifications on data interoperability and harmonization at the EU level. SPMS is participating in and contributing to different projects that are progressing the deliberation and implementation of the future European Health Data Space (EHDS) in terms of primary and secondary use of health data. SPMS is also responsible for managing the Centro de Terminologias Clínicas (*clinical terminology center*) that involves collaborating with different national institutions, such as ACSS, DGS e INSA, to develop semantic catalogues in order to promote data interoperability. Lastly, SPMS is analysing existing AI tools with applications for public health surveillance and also planning the collection of best practices for this purpose.

The National Institute of Public Health of Slovenia NIJZ is a national public health authority and a lawful controller of national healthcare databases. Since 2015, NIJZ is managing national eHealth services and databases. The most comprehensive Central Registry of Patient Data (CRPD), the national platform for exchanging Electronic Health Records (<https://ezdrav.si/en/solutions/crpd/>). The CRPD was used as a baseline for the national COVID-19 Registry, providing automatic registration of positive cases based on real-time collection of test results. In cooperation with the leading national microbiology laboratory, the NIJZ has established real time collection of COVID-19 sequencing results to CRPD and automatic transfer to the national COVID-19 database, from where the data on virus variants is forwarded to ECDC. The technical solution is fully embedded in the national eHealth infrastructure, providing the highest standards of data protection and cybersecurity. The relevant data are findable and accessible to all eligible users and interoperable on a national level. The initial Electronic Health Record (COVID-19 test result, sequencing result) is reusable for epidemiological surveillance. Within EU-HIP project, NIJZ plans to extend the existing solution to support other communicable diseases. Apart from laboratory results for diseases other than COVID-19, Patient summary diagnosis records are planned to be reused where applicable for detection of communicable diseases and building of the national databases. Accordingly, the future databases and IT application the control of communicable diseases will stem from the already established national Electronic Health Record.

CONCLUSION

The process of developing DMP of EU-HIP started already at proposal writing stage. The list of data covered in EU-HIP DMP is specified and updated during the project, and management of the data is discussed proactively. DMP is regularly discussed within the EU-HIP Consortium during the project.

The EU-HIP DMP is expected to be useful to address the challenge arising from the diverse technological platforms and systems used by different member states for data generation, collection, storage, sharing and management. There will be a need to address data formats, data exchange protocols, and data transformation procedures to ensure seamless data integration within the HERA IGTA/MCM system.

There may be variations in data accuracy, completeness, and consistency across different datasets. Rigorous quality control measures, including standardized data validation procedures, to ensure the reliability of the shared data, will be needed for effective utility of the HERA IGTA/MCM system.